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Companies supplying electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning in OECD countries

They grew on average by 1009% between 2005 and 2012

The OECD calculates the companies supplying electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning. The data refers to the period between 2005 and 2022.

Companies supplying electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning in OECD countries in 2022. The data relating to companies supplying electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning in OECD countries for the year 2022 highlight significant differences between the various nations, reflecting the diversity of energy infrastructure and national energy policies. Germany leads the ranking with a total of 65,712 companies, demonstrating a highly developed and diversified energy sector, likely thanks to a combination of large energy companies and a myriad of smaller suppliers contributing to the national energy grid. This diversification could also be attributed to Germany's energy transition policies (Energiewende), which promote renewable energy and energy efficiency. France follows with 36,956 companies, a considerably lower number than Germany, but still significant. This reflects the centralized structure of the French energy sector, dominated by large players such as EDF (Électricité de France), but with a growing presence of smaller companies, especially in the renewable energy sector. Spain and the Czech Republic, with 12,813 and 12,612 companies respectively, show a strong presence of energy suppliers, probably supported by policies favorable to increasing production capacity and the integration of alternative energy sources. Greece, with 12,009 companies, indicates a large and varied energy sector, despite the country's economic challenges. Italy, with 9,417 companies, reflects a diversified energy market, with a growing focus on renewable energy and energy efficiency. Portugal and Turkey, with 6,187 and 5,890 companies respectively, highlight growing energy sectors, supported by investments in energy infrastructure and policies for the diversification of energy sources. Poland and Bulgaria, with 4,476 and 4,119 companies respectively, show expanding energy markets, likely driven by the need to modernize energy infrastructure and reduce dependence on traditional energy sources. Austria, with 3,922 companies, reflects a well-developed energy sector, with a particular focus on renewable energy and energy efficiency. The Netherlands, with 2,763 companies, indicates a dynamic and evolving energy market, with a strong focus on sustainability and innovation. Denmark and Sweden, with 2,238 and 1,949 companies respectively, represent examples of Nordic countries with advanced energy sectors, characterized by a high use of renewable energy and advanced energy management technologies. Hungary, Finland and Norway, with 1,666, 1,456 and 1,327 companies respectively, show stable energy markets with increasing integration of renewable energy sources. Slovenia and Romania, with 1,317 and 1,303 companies, indicate energy sectors in the development phase, supported by policies of modernization and diversification of energy sources. Lithuania and Israel, with 1,285 and 925 companies respectively, reflect smaller but growing energy markets, with a focus on the diversification of energy sources and the adoption of innovative technologies. Serbia, with 891 companies, shows an expanding energy market, supported by reforms and infrastructure investments. Belgium, with 835

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companies, and Slovakia, with 813 companies, highlight developed energy sectors but with potential for further growth and diversification. Ireland and Croatia, with 799 and 661 companies respectively, show dynamic and evolving energy markets, with growing interest in renewable energy. Estonia and Latvia, with 660 and 484 companies respectively, reflect growing energy markets, with a particular focus on energy efficiency and sustainability. Switzerland, with 454 companies, shows a well-developed and highly technological energy market. North Macedonia, Bosnia and Herzegovina and Costa Rica, with 366, 315 and 158 companies respectively, indicate smaller but developing energy markets, with potential for greater expansion and modernisation. Luxembourg, with 123 companies, and Cyprus, with 102 companies, reflect very small energy markets but with growth potential, especially in the integration of renewable energy sources. Finally, Malta, with only 22 companies, represents the smallest energy market among OECD countries, with considerable challenges but also opportunities to develop a more sustainable and modern energy sector.

Companies supplying electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning in OECD countries between 2005 and 2022. Data relating to companies operating in the supply of electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning in OECD countries, comparing the years 2005 and 2022, reveal substantial transformations in the energy sector. Germany, with an impressive increase from 1,461 to 65,712 companies, marks an absolute change of 64,251 companies and a percentage growth of 4,497.74%. This extraordinary increase likely reflects a combination of favorable policies, incentives for renewable energy and a push towards decentralization and diversification of the energy market. France follows with notable growth, going from 2,355 to 36,956 companies, with an absolute change of 34,601 companies and a percentage increase of 1,569.26%. This increase could be attributed to significant reforms in the energy sector, the opening of the market to new players and a strong push towards renewable energy. The Czech Republic shows exceptional growth, with an increase from 1,089 to 12,612 businesses, marking an absolute change of 11,523 businesses and a percentage increase of 1,158.13%. This data suggests a significant expansion of the energy sector, probably supported by infrastructure investments and energy market liberalization policies. Bulgaria also recorded a marked increase, going from 204 to 4,119 companies, with an absolute change of 3,915 companies and a percentage growth of 2,019.12%. This increase is indicative of a rapidly developing energy market, potentially stimulated by incentive policies and the need to modernize existing infrastructure. Italy, with an increase from 1,759 to 9,417 companies, highlights an absolute variation of 7,658 companies and a percentage growth of 535.36%. This suggests a significant expansion of the sector, likely influenced by the liberalization of the energy market and the increased use of renewable energy. Spain, going from 2,383 to 12,813 companies, shows an absolute variation of 10,430 companies and a percentage increase of 537.68%. This reflects strong growth in the sector, supported by favorable energy policies and the integration of new technologies and energy sources. In Austria, the number of businesses increased from 1,250 to 3,922, marking an absolute change of 2,672 businesses and a percentage growth of 313.76%. This increase can be attributed to a combination of renewable energy incentive policies and investments in energy infrastructure. Belgium saw an increase from 109 to 835 companies, with an absolute change of 726 companies and a percentage growth of 766.05%. This increase suggests significant energy market expansion, likely spurred by government reforms and incentives. In Portugal, the number of businesses grew from 500 to 6,187, marking an absolute change of 5,687 businesses and a percentage growth of 1,237.4%. This increase is indicative of a rapidly expanding energy market, supported by incentive policies and investments in energy infrastructure. Hungary recorded an increase from 389 to 1,666 enterprises, with an absolute change of 1,277 enterprises and a percentage growth of 428.28%. This reflects an

expansion of the energy sector, potentially influenced by investments and liberalization policies. Slovakia, with an increase from 183 to 813 companies, shows an absolute change of 630 companies and a percentage growth of 444.26%. This suggests significant growth in the sector, likely supported by reforms and incentives for renewable energy. Slovenia saw an increase from 317 to 1,317 companies, with an absolute change of 1,000 companies and a percentage growth of 415.46%. This reflects an expansion of the energy market, supported by incentive policies and investments in new technologies. Lithuania recorded an increase from 184 to 1,285 enterprises, with an absolute change of 1,101 enterprises and a percentage growth of 698.37%. This suggests significant growth in the energy sector, likely influenced by government reforms and incentives. In Denmark, the number of businesses grew from 2,001 to 2,238, marking an absolute change of 237 businesses and a percentage growth of 111.84%. This increase reflects a stability of the sector with a slight expansion, probably supported by sustainability policies. Estonia saw an increase from 187 to 660 companies, with an absolute change of 473 companies and a percentage growth of 352.94%. This suggests an expanding energy market, supported by investments and liberalization policies. In Latvia, the number of businesses has increased or from 286 to 484, marking an absolute change of 198 companies and a percentage growth of 169.23%. This reflects moderate growth in the sector, likely supported by reforms and incentives. Romania recorded an increase from 256 to 1,303 companies, with an absolute change of 1,047 companies and a percentage growth of 508.98%. This suggests a significant expansion of the energy sector, supported by modernization policies and incentives. Finally, Costa Rica saw an increase from 108 to 158 businesses, with an absolute change of 50 businesses and a percentage growth of 146.30%. This reflects moderate growth in the energy market, probably influenced by incentive policies and infrastructure investments.

Conclusions. The companies supplying electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning in OECD countries grew on average by 1009% between 2005 and 2012. The countries in which the number of companies supplying electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning is Germany grew the most with +4497.74%, Bulgaria with 2019.12%, France with +1569.26%. The countries in which these companies had a lower growth rate are Latvia with +169.23%, Costa Rica with 146.30% and Denmark with +111.84%. Considering 2022, it appears that more than 50% of the companies operating in this sector are located in just two countries, namely Germany with 65,712 units and France with 36,956 units.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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